

Science

A PRELIMINARY ETHNOBOTANICAL SURVEY OF SEHORE DISTRICT OF MADHYA PRADESH

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Abstract

The present communication deals with the ethnobotanical study of Sehore. Sehore district with an area of 6579 km² lying between the North Latitudes 22 0 33' 30'' & 22 0 40' 25'' and East Longitudes 78 0 26' 00'' and 78 0 02' 00''. The normal rainfall of district is 1217.7 mm. The study revealed with 41 taxa belonging to 40 genera and 30 angiospermic families that are used by the tribal people to cure various human diseases.

Keywords: Ethnobotany; Medicinal Plants; Tribes; Angiospermic.

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1. Introduction

Ethnobotany or Medicobotany deals with the relationship between human societies and plants. Sehore is situated 39 Km. away from Bhopal towards south. More than 11% of the total population of this area belongs to tribal community (e.g. Bhil, Gond, Korku, Pardhi).

A review of literature on ethno botany indicates that although a lot of work has been done in India in general and M.P. in particular (Jain, 1963, 1965; Jain & Tarafdar, 1968; Maheshwari et al. 1981; Maheshwar, 1990 and Oommachan & Masih, 1991, Mudgal et al.1997; Singh et al.2001) but it has been mainly limited to mandla, Bastar, Balaghat and Jabalpur districts only. As regards the Southern M.P. a little work on ethnobotany has been done (Mahajan, 1990; 1995; Mahajan & Patel, 2003; and Mahajan et al, 2003).The present investigation was undertaken to fill the gap.

2. Materials and Methods

The present study is the outcomes of exhaustive field survey under taken for the period of two years from January 2014 to December 2015.During the survey and collection, the data has been

generated from the tribal medicinemen in different villages of Sehore district. Frequent visits were made at regular intervals in the selected villages of Bhil, Gond, Korku & Pardhi. The plants used by the tribal people to cure various diseases were collected with the consultation of old experienced tribal persons and tribal medicine man.

The species collected during the survey were scientifically identified with their Botanical names, local names, names of families to which they belong, plant parts used and medicinal use.

The list of ethno medicinal plants used by tribal peoples is being presented. The plants are arranged in alphabetical order.

S.No	Name of Plant	Local Name	Family	Parts Used	Medicinal Use
1	<i>Abelmoschus moschatus</i> L.	Jungli bhindi	Malvaceae	Fruits	asthma
2	<i>Abrus precatorius</i> L.	Ratti	Fabaceae (Papilionaceae)	Root, Seed & Leaf	blood purifier, migraine & Wounds
3	<i>Achyranthes aspera</i> L.	Chirchitta	Amaranthaceae	Root	pneumonia
4	<i>Adhatoda vasica</i> Nees	Adusa	Acanthaceae	Leaves & Roots	asthma & bronchitis
5	<i>Aegle marmelos</i> L.	Bel-patra	Rutaceae	Fruits	swelling, dysentery & diarrhea
6	<i>Aloe barbadensis</i> Mill.	Gwarpatha	Liliaceae	Fleshy Leaves	diarrhea, skin Diseases, headache,
7	<i>Annona squamosa</i> L.	Sitaphal	Annonaceae	Leaf, bark, Seed & Fruit	tumor & fever,
8	<i>Argemone maxicana</i> L.	Satyanasi	Papaveraceae	Roots & Seeds	skin diseases fever & worms
9	<i>Aristolochia bracteata</i> Retz.	Girdhan	Aristolochiaceae	Leaves, Seeds & Roots	Jaundice, snake bite & scorpion sting
10	<i>Barleria prionitis</i> L.	Katsala	Acanthaceae	Leaves	toothache
11	<i>Bombax ceiba</i> L.	Semal	Bombacaceae	Seeds	typhoid
12	<i>Calotropis procera</i> R.Br.	Aak	Asclepediaceae	Latex	ring worn
13	<i>Cardiospermum halicacabum</i> L.	Kanphuti	Sapindaceae	Roots, Leaves & Seeds	ear trouble
14	<i>Cassia tora</i> L.	Punwar	Fabaceae (Cesalpiniaceae)	Seeds & Leaves	asthma & skin disease
15	<i>Chlorophytum arundinaceum</i> Baker	Safed musli	Liliaceae	Root	arthritis & diabetes
16	<i>Crateva religiosa</i> Forst.	barna	Capparidaceae	Leaves & Bark	asthma & bronchitis
17	<i>Curcuma longa</i>	Haldi	Zingiberaaceae	Rhizome	indigestion, throat infection & cold
18	<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> L.	Nagar motha	Cyperaceae	Whole plant	fever & dysmenorrheal

19	<i>Datura metel</i> L.	Kala Datura	Solanaceae	Leaves	asthma, skin disease & fever
20	<i>Gardenia turgida</i> Roxb.	Phetra	Rubiaceae	Gum of the plant	constipation, bronchitis, vomiting.,
21	<i>Helicteres isora</i> L.	Marophali	Sterculiaceae	Pods	diarrhea, dysentery & snakebite
22	<i>Ixora coccinea</i> L.	Jungle Geranium	Rubiaceae	Flowers	dysentery, ulcers & scabies
23	<i>Lawsonia inermis</i>	Mehndi	Lythraceae	Leaves & Bark	diarrhea, amoebic dysentery & fever,
24	<i>Leucas cephalotus</i> spreng.	Gattatumba	Lamiaceae	Flowers	cough and cold
25	<i>Jasminum Sambac</i> L.	Mogra	Oleaceae	Leaves & Flowers	worms & skin diseases
26	<i>Linum usitatissimum</i> L.	Alsi	Linaceae	Seeds	diarrhea & boils
27	<i>Mucuna prurita</i> Hook	Kavanch	Fabaceae (Papilionaceae)	Seeds	cough , asthma & constipation
28	<i>Malvastrum tricuspidatum</i> A. Gray.	Khareti	Malvaceae	Leaves & Bark	diabetes
29	<i>Nymphaea stellata</i> Willd.	Chota Kamal	Nymphaeaceae	Rhizomes & other parts	liver disorders , urinary disorders
30	<i>Nymphaea rubra</i> roxb.	Lal Kamal	Nymphaeaceae	Rhizomes & other parts	diarrhea & dysentery
31	<i>Ocimum basilicum</i> L.	Marua	Lamiaceae	Leaves	earache, nausea & dysentery
32	<i>Psoralea corylifolia</i> L.	Babchi	Fabaceae (Papilionaceae)	Seeds	leucoderma & leprosy
33	<i>Peristrophe bicalyculata</i> Nees.	Atrilal	Acanthaceae	Roots	snake bite
34	<i>.Polyanthia longifolia</i> Thw.	False Ashok	Annonaceae	Stem & Bark	hypertension, , Fever & Diabetes
35	<i>Ricinus communis</i> L.	Arandi	Euphorbiaceae	Seeds	arthritis ,diarrhea & dehydration
36	<i>Syzygium cuminii</i>	Jamun	Myrtaaceae	Leaves, Fruits & Bark	diabetes, cough, asthma & bronchitis,
37	<i>Tinoposora cordifolia</i> Miers	Guduchi, Gloy	Menispermaceae	Whole plant	jaundice, diabetes, & hepatitis,
38	<i>Terminalia arjuna</i> Wight & Arn.	Arjun	Combretaceae	Bark	cordiovascular diseases & blood pressure
39	<i>Tridax procumbens</i> L.	Ghav Pani	Asteraceae	Leaves	skin disease, cuts and wounds
40	<i>Vitex negundo</i> L.	Nirgundi	Verbenaceae	Leaves, Roots & Flowers	liver problem & diarrhea
41	<i>Withania somnifera</i> L.	Asgand	Solanaceae	Roots	Rheumatism & tuberculosis

3. Result & Discussion

The study revealed in all 41 taxa belonging to 40 genera and 30 angiospermic families that are used by the tribal people to cure various human diseases. Few plants of this locality possess potential of better economic exploitation. Important among these are *Abrus precatorius* (Ratti), *Aristolochia bracteata* (Girdhan), *Chlorophytum arundinaceum* (Safed musli), *Gardenia turgid* (Phetra), *Helicteres isora* (Marophali), *Vitex nigundo* (Nirgundi), *Withania somnifera* (Asgand). The result of present study provides evidence that medicinal plants continue to play an important role in healthcare system of tribal communities.

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